

Words As Shields and Swords: The Pervasive Influence of Pentecostal Language in Nigeria

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Abstract

Nigerian Pentecostalism has emerged as a significant socio-cultural force, exerting profound influence across various aspects of daily life, including linguistic practices. The movement has not only facilitated the emergence of new lexical expressions that reinforce religious dogmatism in a restrictive sense but has also contributed to their widespread deployment in social discourse in a more flexible and pervasive manner. Through innovative media, Pentecostal ideology, particularly in the form of warfare prayers and vernacular expressions has deeply permeated societal interactions, enabling individuals to appropriate these linguistic forms in popular culture to articulate diverse ideologies and identities. This study critically examines how ordinary Nigerians utilize Pentecostal expressions as rhetorical instruments of both offense and defense against perceived threats to their personal and communal progress, as well as tools for social engagement and interaction. Adopting an analytical approach, the study employs Norman Fairclough's (1995) Critical Discourse Analysis as its theoretical framework and draws on empirical data from participant observations and unstructured interviews. The findings reveal that the integration of Pentecostal language into everyday discourse reflects broader sociocultural transformations and underscores the profound impact of religious movements on societal norms and values. Ultimately, the study highlights the intertwined roles of language and religion as foundational instruments in shaping human society.

Keywords: Critical Discourse Analysis, ideology, language, Pentecostalism, religion, warfare prayer

Introduction

Language is a fundamental component of social life, intricately interwoven with the structures and dynamics of human interaction. It serves as the primary medium through which individuals access and interpret the thoughts of others, as well as the principal vehicle for transmitting cultural knowledge. Consequently, all communicative exchanges occur within a social context that imposes certain constraints on linguistic choices, shaping both the form and content of communication. These linguistic patterns, in turn, reflect and reinforce broader social constructs, mirroring how individuals perceive and navigate their sociocultural realities. As an exclusively human phenomenon, language cannot be studied in isolation from culture. The reciprocal influence between society and language is well established: social structures shape linguistic practices, and linguistic practices, in turn, shape societal norms and cultural identities (Lut & Starenkova, 2022). Understanding language use, therefore, provides critical insights into the structure and function of society, as language behaviors are informed by broader communal expectations and discursive conventions.

In the Nigerian context, Pentecostalism has played a pivotal role in shaping linguistic expressions, particularly through its emphasis on spiritual warfare and the rhetoric of divine intervention. Over the years, Pentecostal discourse has normalized the belief in ubiquitous spiritual adversaries, leading to the widespread adoption of "warfare prayer" models, speech acts imbued with performative and rhetorical force, as a means of engaging with perceived threats in both religious and secular settings. As Wariboko (2016) argues, within West African Pentecostalism, language serves as a tool for meaning-making, identity construction, and social differentiation, creating symbolic battlegrounds where theological and cultural discourses intersect. Through common expressions, Pentecostal adherents articulate new meanings, establish hierarchical distinctions (e.g., superior versus inferior, past versus future), and negotiate social power dynamics.

This study explores the ways in which Pentecostal expressions have transcended their strictly religious origins to permeate everyday social interactions, thereby reshaping the linguistic landscape of contemporary Nigeria. The pervasive influence of Pentecostal theology and discourse, amplified by the media has not only left an indelible mark on communication practices but has also facilitated the incorporation of spiritual warfare vernacular into secular domains. These expressions are frequently deployed not only as mechanisms for confronting unseen adversaries but also as means of articulating emotions, asserting agency, and navigating interpersonal relationships. Wariboko (2016) describes this phenomenon as "correlated theology," wherein religious language is structured around associative rather than strictly logical connections, enabling a fluid adaptation of theological concepts to diverse social contexts.

Expressions such as *"I reject it,"* *"it is not my portion,"* *"back to sender,"* *"Holy Ghost fire,"* *"Blood of Jesus,"* *"testimony,"* *"deliverance,"* and *"binding and casting"* have become integral components of the Nigerian English lexicon and vernaculars. These phrases function as linguistic markers of Pentecostal power and ideology, deeply embedded in Nigerian social life. The choice of these religiously influenced expressions is contingent upon factors such as the social context, the interlocutors' emotional states, and the perceived nature of a given interaction, whether it be an assertion of identity, a reaction to hostility, or a demonstration of solidarity. Importantly, while these expressions originate in religious discourse, their use in everyday communication often transcends their theological meanings, reflecting instead the speaker's unique interpretations and communicative intentions.

The sociolinguistic transformation driven by Pentecostalism has resulted in the proliferation of biblical references and theological constructs within everyday discourse, even in non-religious settings. Community members actively engage with Pentecostal language, adapting and reinterpreting its expressions to address their experiences, needs, and social interactions. According to Uwen (2020), imprecations and curses, stylistic elements of language popularized by Pentecostalism, have become integral to contemporary Nigerian communication, serving as both rhetorical strategies and cultural signifiers. These expressions function as mechanisms for asserting agencies, denouncing unfavorable utterances, and negotiating power dynamics in various settings, including markets, bus stations, hospitals, and police checkpoints.

This study delves into the profound influence of Pentecostal discourse on language use in Nigeria, particularly in the way spiritual idioms have been woven into everyday social interactions. Across markets, streets, homes, and public spaces, Pentecostal expressions have evolved beyond their strictly religious origins to serve as powerful linguistic tools for self-assertion, identity formation, and the negotiation of power. These phrases, once confined to the realm of prayer and spiritual warfare, now shape how individuals engage with one another, respond to conflict, and affirm their place within society. At the heart of this inquiry is an exploration of how community members have appropriated Pentecostal warfare vernacular, repurposing it as both an offensive and defensive strategy in their daily interactions. Whether used to counter perceived threats, reinforce personal convictions, or establish social solidarity, these expressions have become deeply embedded in Nigerian popular culture. They serve not only as rhetorical devices but also as markers of belonging, signaling shared beliefs and collective experiences.

Beyond their function in interpersonal exchanges, Pentecostal expressions also play a crucial role in shaping identities and social hierarchies. This study examines how individuals strategically deploy spiritual idioms to assert dominance, challenge authority, or navigate social structures. From everyday conversations to political rhetoric, these expressions have become an essential part of how Nigerians articulate power, resistance, and communal identity. By tracing the integration of Pentecostal discourse into secular communication, this study sheds light on the dynamic relationship between language, religion, and society. It reveals how linguistic expressions, born from a deeply spiritual worldview, have transcended their original contexts to influence broader cultural and social narratives, reshaping the communicative landscape of Nigeria.

Language As a Social and Cultural Construct

Schegloff (1987:208) has observed that language serves as the "primordial locus for sociality," highlighting its foundational role in human interaction. Beyond being one of the most intricate modes of communication, language functions as a powerful instrument for transmitting and reinforcing social ideals and perceptions (Nnorom & Ogunnaike, 2018). The complexity of language as a communicative resource, with its fluid boundaries and indeterminate internal structure, has been emphasized by Halliday (1978), who argues that its mechanisms defy fixed categorization. From this perspective, linguistic scholars continuously grapple with issues of definitional adequacy, leading to a multiplicity of assumptions about the nature of language and its role in shaping human experience.

Language is instrumental in defining social entities and mediating their experiences within the broader societal framework. Social practices and processes, while conditioned by extralinguistic factors, exist in a dialectical relationship with language itself (Fairclough, 1989). As Fairclough asserts, language is an integral component of society, making linguistic phenomena inherently social, just as social phenomena are, to some degree, constituted through language. The pervasive influence of language in social life is evident in its role as the principal vehicle for cultural transmission and as the primary means through which individuals' access and interpret the thoughts and beliefs of others. Consequently, every communicative exchange is embedded within a specific social context, which constrains and shapes linguistic choices. The way participants define their social environment, their perceptions of others' knowledge, intentions, and identities, and the claims they make about themselves, and others all influence the form and substance of their speech acts.

Pentecostalism and its Ideological Dimensions

Language and religion are so intertwined that different religious groups have created distinct identities for themselves by using language in ways that distinguish them from others. In this case, language serves to facilitate compliance with religious values, experiences, beliefs, and practices. Glossolalia, also known as '*speaking in tongues*', is a common example of linguistic identity within a religious group. "Those within a religious community have their own way of using languages; their own 'religious Language' that can only really be understood by being a part of the 'language game' (Ottuh & Godwin, 2011). Horden (1964), cited in Ottuh and Godwin (2011), argues that religious language is not conceived of as "metaphysical," but rather as more directly related to our human experiences and needs. Thus, Pentecostalism has led to the development of a repertoire of ideology, thoughts,

imaginations, expressions, and images that convey the urgency of countering negative utterances from hostile interactants who are perceived to engender others providence before it is too late (Marshall, 2016).

Pentecostal ideological assumptions, both within Africa and on a global scale, have been the subject of extensive scholarly inquiry across various disciplines. Existing research has explored diverse themes, including the movement's engagement in sociopolitical affairs in which scholars such as (Marshall, 2016; Wariboko, 2017; Adalaku, 2022, 2023; Burack, 2020) have explored. The contributions of Pentecostalism to poverty alleviation and social welfare initiatives have been extensively investigated by notable scholars including (Oyelade & Omobowale, 2019; Gukurume, 2022). Another influential area in Pentecostal research which has generated global interest is the concept of demonology. Notable scholars that have made significant contributions around demonology include (Opoku Onyinah, 2002, 2012; Hackett, 2003a; Richman, 2019; Ojo, 2018, Coleman, 2017) and many others. Furthermore, scholars have examined the intersection of language and religion, particularly the evolving linguistic expressions within contemporary Christianity and their impact on National languages and sociolinguistic behavior of community members such as (Alsaawi, 2022; Tsoraya, Primalaini & Asbar, 2022; Uwen, 2020; Kperogi, 2019; Sekerdej, Kossowska, & Czernatowicz-Kukuczka, 2018; Supardi, Hindarto, & Ridlo, 2018). Additionally, (Knott, 2022; Frederiks, 2015; Ryan, 2014; Oppong, 2013) investigated the relationship between religion, power, and identity.

While these studies have explored Pentecostalism from diverse perspectives, they collectively highlight the centrality of Pentecostal theology especially as it relates to spiritual encounters and modes of prayer as key ideological strands within the broader movement. This framework conceptualizes life as a spiritual battleground, where believers engage in spiritual warfare against malevolent forces and their perceived human agents, operating within both social and spiritual domains. The existing scholarship has illuminated the connections between contemporary Pentecostalism and socioeconomic and political struggles, particularly in relation to poverty in Nigeria, Africa, and other developing regions. Though many of these studies made references to the role of Pentecostal vernacular in constructing new meanings and shaping identity dynamics, there remains a notable gap in research concerning the adaptation and utilization of Pentecostal vernacular expressions as linguistic tools for negotiation, resistance, and social engagement in everyday culture. This study seeks to address this gap by examining how Pentecostal vernacular, particularly warfare expressions, functions as both a rhetorical weapon and a shield in Nigerian sociocultural interactions.

An Overview of Pentecostal Religious Renaissance in Nigeria

Pentecostalism is a diverse movement within evangelical, charismatic Protestant Christianity. It gained prominence in Nigeria during the 1970s, especially among university students who formed interdenominational fellowships like Scripture Union (SU) to promote "born-again" Christianity and holiness. As Nigeria's economy grew, Pentecostal ministries expanded in the 1980s, distancing themselves from African traditional beliefs. However, amid economic challenges, due to collapsing commodity prices and IMF-imposed conditionalities, the church shifted their message from sanctification to prosperity, healing, and deliverance (Wariboko, 2017; Adalaku, 2022). From the 1990s onward, Nigerian Pentecostal churches have become centers of religious and cultural innovation, appealing to a wide range of socioeconomic groups. They adapt African traditional religious practices, with a message emphasizing spiritual empowerment. Major denominations feature bureaucracies and influential pastors, positioning themselves as agents of national transformation. Nigerian Pentecostalism adapts its theology to cultural contexts, fostering a worldview that sees the supernatural as integral to daily life and shaping prayer practices. The movement's growth has been amplified by innovative communication strategies, using media to reach a broad audience and expand globally. These strategies have led to the spread of Pentecostal theology, with new churches emerging in diverse spaces, reinforcing a delocalized sense of identity and community (Marshall- Fratani, 1998; Olupona, 2008; Wariboko, 2017; Adalaku 2022, 2023; Richman 2020 & Nel 2019).

The strategic utilization of media, particularly with the proliferation of digital technologies and the expansion of communication channels, including the internet, social media platforms, and mobile devices such as smartphones, laptops, and tablets,

has significantly extended the reach of Pentecostalism. These technological advancements have facilitated broader accessibility to Pentecostal theology, prayer practices, testimonies, linguistic expressions, and idiomatic frameworks, enabling their dissemination beyond traditional ecclesiastical settings. A key consequence of this media-driven expansion is the increasing public engagement with Pentecostal vernacular culture, particularly in the domain of spiritual warfare. Through this process, distinctive theological expressions and symbolic vocabularies are integrated into daily life, reinforcing their functionality and perceived relevance in navigating complex socioeconomic, political, and cultural landscapes. Moreover, the widespread appeal of Pentecostalism and its oral traditions is frequently intensified by economic hardships, systemic corruption, declining quality of life, social instability, and the broader existential uncertainties that characterize contemporary society. These conditions have further incentivized individuals to incorporate sacred language and spiritual frameworks into everyday discourse within secular public spaces, thereby shaping both personal and collective responses to adversity.

Theoretical Framework : Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA)

Norman Fairclough's (1995) Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) provides the analytical foundation for this study. CDA is a methodological approach that examines language as discourse, meaning that language is not an isolated system but is dialectically interconnected with broader social processes (Fairclough & Graham, 2002, p. 188). The origins of CDA can be traced to classical rhetoric, text linguistics, sociolinguistics, applied linguistics, and pragmatics (Wodak, 2011). Additionally, it draws from critical linguistics, which was pioneered by scholars such as Kress & Hodge (1979) and Fowler et al. (1979). These early works were influenced by Halliday's (1978, 1985) systemic functional linguistics and theories of ideology (Fairclough, 1993; Rogers, 2003).

Critical linguistics emphasizes the role of power and ideology in language, aiming to uncover the social meanings embedded in discourse by analyzing linguistic structures in relation to broader social contexts (Fowler et al., 1979, pp. 195–196). CDA extends this perspective by considering how power dynamics are reflected in discourse and how language both constructs and is conditioned by society (Fairclough & Wodak, 1997, p. 258).

Key Tenets of CDA

According to Fairclough and Wodak (1997), CDA is distinguished by the following principles:

1. CDA addresses social problems.
2. Power relations are discursive.
3. Discourse constitutes society and culture.
4. Discourse performs ideological functions.
5. Discourse is historical.
6. The link between text and society is mediated.
7. Discourse analysis is interpretative and explanatory.
8. Discourse is a form of social action.

A central concern of CDA is the examination of power as a fundamental condition in social life. This includes analyzing how power struggles and ideological battles manifest within discourse across various social spaces and genres (Wodak & Koller, 2008). While language plays a crucial role in maintaining or challenging power structures, it does not inherently generate power rather, it serves as a means through which power is expressed, negotiated, and contested in social institutions. Fairclough (2001a) argues that while sociolinguistics effectively describes linguistic variation based on social factors, it often fails to explain how such variations contribute to power relations and social struggles. CDA addresses this gap by conceptualizing discourse as a form of social practice that is, language is not merely a tool for communication but an instrument of social action (Austin, 1962; Levinson, 1983). This means that spoken or written statements function as speech acts, shaping social realities through assertions, promises, warnings, and other forms of discourse.

CDA provides a methodological framework for analyzing real-life instances of discourse, highlighting how ideological assumptions are embedded in language use. It reveals how discourse constructs knowledge, social identities, and power relations (Wodak, 2009, p. 37). Scholars such as Van Dijk (1993) argue that the goal of CDA is not merely to analyze linguistic structures but also to

examine their social functions, particularly how language maintains or disrupts power hierarchies. This study adopts a qualitative and descriptive approach, utilizing participant observation, unstructured interviews, and field notes to explore how language functions as a vehicle for framing sociocultural and religious experiences in Nigerian society. The analysis provides insights into power relations, ideological leanings, and the evolving dynamics of social interaction.

Language and Religion in Sociolinguistics

Religion has long been a significant factor in sociolinguistics, influencing language variation, maintenance, and policy. Early studies (e.g., Haugen, 1953; Hutchinson, 1959; Ferguson, 1959, 1968, 1982; Fishman, Kloss & Hofman, 1966) recognized the interplay between language and religion but did not systematically examine this relationship from a sociolinguistic perspective. More recent works such as (Omoniyi & Fishman, 2006) have expanded the field, demonstrating that language and religion are inseparable components of culture. Scholars have analyzed religious language within liturgical settings (Crystal, 1966), while others have examined its role in non-religious discourse, including its influence on popular culture, politics, and social interactions (Uwem, 2020; Kperogi, 2019; Offiong, 2003). In Nigeria, religious expressions permeate everyday language and extend beyond sacred spaces, influencing colloquial and political discourse. However, in South Africa, scholars such as Adebayo & Zulu (2021) observe a shift in church language, where secular expressions have infiltrated religious discourse, sometimes altering the spiritual focus from themes of salvation and healing to material prosperity and success.

Language and social life are inextricably linked. Discourse serves as both a reflection and a driver of social change, influencing power dynamics, identity formation, and ideological constructions. As Witzak-Plisiecka (2013) argues, religious rituals rely on the performative and rhetorical power of language, shaping spiritual experiences through discourse. Similarly, Pishghadam et al. (2013) and Shokym et al. (2022) assert that religious and cultural beliefs are encoded in language, making it a central mechanism for preserving and transmitting collective knowledge. The present study contributes to the growing body of research on language, religion, and power, illustrating how discourse constructs and negotiates social realities. By employing CDA, the study uncovers the linguistic strategies through which ideological assumptions and power relations are embedded in religious, particularly in everyday communication, and sociopolitical contexts.

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative case study design, an approach that facilitates an in-depth empirical inquiry into a contemporary sociolinguistic phenomenon within its real-life context. A qualitative case study allows for the systematic exploration of a phenomenon through multiple data sources and interpretive lenses, thereby revealing its multifaceted nature (Baxter & Jack, 2008). Given the study's focus on the integration of Pentecostal vernacular into everyday discourse, purposive sampling was employed to identify communicative settings where this phenomenon is most prevalent. These include busy streets, markets, bus stations, traffic checkpoints, hospitals, viewing centers, commercial vehicles, and other public interaction spaces across diverse discourse domains.

Data Collection

The study utilizes both primary and secondary data sources. Primary data were derived from natural spoken language interactions among discourse participants within the selected settings. To ensure a representative corpus, a randomly selected primary case was chosen for in-depth analysis, with expressions extracted from it complemented by relevant linguistic instances from other observed scenarios. This methodological approach facilitated the construction of a robust dataset that captures the dynamism of Pentecostal vernacular usage in everyday interactions. Data collection methods included participant observation and unstructured interviews. Participant observation enabled the researchers to document linguistic interactions in their natural contexts, while unstructured interviews provided participants the opportunity to articulate their perspectives on language use, thereby offering

deeper insights into the sociolinguistic and cultural dimensions of Pentecostal discourse. Data collection tools included a mobile phone's audiovisual recording capabilities for capturing spontaneous interactions and field notes for documenting contextual details and researcher reflections. Additionally, secondary data were sourced from library research, published texts, and other relevant literature, providing a broader theoretical framework for interpreting the findings.

Data Analysis

The data collected were systematically analyzed through thematic classification, with three primary analytical themes emerging:

1. Instances of Power – Examining how Pentecostal vernacular functions as a mechanism for asserting authority, influence, or control in various discourse contexts.
2. Ideological Dimensions – Investigating how linguistic expressions reflect underlying religious and sociocultural ideologies.
3. Identity Representations – Exploring the role of Pentecostal vernacular in self-presentation, group identity formation, and sociocultural affiliation.

Within these thematic categories, sacred linguistic expressions were extracted and analyzed to illustrate how the integration of Pentecostal vernacular into everyday discourse serves as a powerful tool for self-assertion, identity negotiation, and the reinforcement of ideological perspectives. Further analysis was conducted to elucidate how these expressions reflect broader sociocultural transformations and underscore the influence of religious movements on societal norms and values. By employing multiple qualitative research methods, this study ensures a rich, contextualized understanding of the entrenchment of Pentecostal vernacular within everyday linguistic interactions. The findings contribute to broader discussions on the intersection of language, power, and religious identity within Lagos' socio-religious landscape.

Data Presentation and Discussion

Lagos is the commercial as well as the Pentecostal hub of Nigeria with a population of over 16 million people according to - UN, population prospects cited in (Macrotrends, 2024). Life in Lagos is vibrant, fast paced, and filled with contrasts. As Nigeria's economic and cultural heart, Lagos offers abundant opportunities in business, tech, and entertainment, drawing people from across the country and beyond. The city is alive day and night, with a dynamic blend of local markets, street food, music, and nightlife. However, life in Lagos also comes with its challenges. The city's dense population creates daily traffic jams, and other environmental issues as infrastructure often struggles to keep up with the needs of its over sixteen million residents. The traffic in Lagos can turn even short commutes into hours-long journeys, leading to frustration and stress, in addition to worsening socioeconomic challenges in daily life. For residents and visitors alike, Lagos' notorious traffic is a test of patience and adaptability, requiring resourcefulness and resilience to navigate the city's urban sprawl. Despite these challenges, Lagosians are known for their resilience, enterprising spirit, and ability to thrive in the face of urban challenges, making the city an energetic and ever-evolving metropolis.

One of the most intriguing elements of Lagos, as well as other Nigerian cities, particularly in the south, is the significant impact of Pentecostal language on the local sociolinguistic landscape. In marketplaces, for example, traders use Pentecostal expressions to interact with their current and potential customers. Often, these expressions are used humorously or sarcastically as a strategy to attract attention. For instance, the researcher once observed a man selling women's dresses who was trying to persuade a lady to buy one by saying, "Sister, this dress go fit you very well, na correct dress! I swear, if you wear this dress, ehh, you go give testimony." Here, the trader implied that wearing the dress would make the woman attractive enough to attract suitors, leading her to testify about her good fortune in church. In another instance, a trader selling women's underwear called to a potential customer, saying, "Aunty, I have all types and sizes. Look at this one, you fit try am; testing is free. I bet if you wear am, ehh, Oga go speak in tongues," suggesting humorously that if the lady wears the underwear, her partner would not be able to resist her. Warfare prayer forms and imprecations are also often deployed especially when there is disagreement in price bargaining. Additionally, during encounters with law enforcement, it's not uncommon to hear expressions such as

“God is my witness,” “Holy ghost fire consume you,” “back to sender,” “it is not my portion” or “I am covered by the blood of Jesus” and “God punish you” used as responses by people who feel mistreated or upset. Warfare language has become a frequent tool for addressing minor hostilities, frustrations, or conflicts in public spaces like markets, streets, hospitals, and public transport. In its most basic forms, language is a link in coordinated human activity and a component of human behavior. It is a mode of action rather than a tool for introspection.

These interactions recorded in Lagos are often as entertaining and humorous as they are intense. Nowadays, rather than intervening in conflict situations, onlookers are more inclined to record these events, sharing them online in real time to generate content and spark discussions. Confrontations involving the appropriation of Pentecostal warfare vernacular have become more frequent, driven by socioeconomic and political pressures that leave people feeling tense and reactive to minor provocations. The primary data for this study comes from one such incident, recorded by the researcher, between two *danfos* (minibuses) drivers at a bus stop on Lagos Island. The exchange between these two individuals forms the central narrative for this study, highlighting its main arguments and research focus. The analysis applies Fairclough’s Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) framework, focusing on power dynamics, identity, and representation.

Lagos faces constant traffic congestion, especially during peak hours, as millions of commuters, street vendors, and commercial vehicles like *danfos* (minibuses) and *kekes* (tricycle taxis) navigate its narrow, poorly maintained roads. The city's infrastructure struggles to manage this traffic, worsened by limited public transit and heavy reliance on private and informal transportation. Commercial drivers, known for impatience, recklessness, and frequent traffic violations, compete for passengers while dealing with harassment from “*agberos*” (touts) demanding fees at bus stops and *LASMAN* (the state traffic management authority). Passengers endure these challenges, breakdowns, and severe traffic jams, often resulting in frustration, disputes, and, at times, confrontations. One such incident occurred when a driver attempted to bypass traffic to pick up passengers, only to be blocked by another driver vying for the same crowd. In their rush, Driver 2 hit the back of the vehicle of Driver 1 sparking a fierce argument. Both drivers angrily accused each other, with tensions rising and harsh words exchanged, nearly escalating to a physical fight before the police intervened. Throughout the confrontation, both men employed Pentecostal language and expressions to assert their identities and intentions. As soon as the accident occurred, they jumped out of their vehicles, loudly accusing each other in a heated verbal exchange that unfolded as follows:

Driver 1: *Alaye* (Yoruba word used derogatorily to address a male – could mean hoodlum, tout etc.) come see wetin you do my vehicle and to God who made me, if you talk nonsense now, I go use this bottle scatter your head. Which kind nonsense be dis? You drink “*ogogoro*” (local dry gin) this early morning? That trouble wey you dey find, you go see am today. (*Alaye* see what you have done to my vehicle and to God who made me, if you talk nonsense now, I will use this bottle to shatter your head. What nonsense is this? Did you drink alcohol early this morning or what? That trouble you are looking for, you will see it today).

Driver 2: Na you drink “*ogogoro*.” You no dey see? E be like say something dey worry you. (it is you who drank alcohol. Can’t you see? It is like something is wrong with you?)

Driver 1: “*Were*,” (mad man)- God punish you. Thunder fire you and your generation. E be like say your village people dey do you (You are mad. God will punish you. Thunder will strike you and your generation. It is like your village people are manipulating you).

Driver 2: “*Back to sender*,” “*Holy Ghost fire!*” Na you wey him head no correct and na you wey them don curse. Holy ghost fire burn you and your entire generation, Mumu. (*Back to sender*. It’s you whose head is not correct and it’s you that is under a curse. Holy ghost fire burn you and your entire generation. Fool!)

Driver 1: if you no take time for this Lagos, you go *kpai* you for nothing. Bet me! You go fix my bus. No be you hit me for back? You no dey go anywhere. I go teach you lesson today. You no know wetin you dey do. Holy ghost fire consume you. Bastard! Mumu (You will fix my bus. Are you not

the one that hit the back of my vehicle? You are not going anywhere. I will teach you a lesson today. You don't know who you are messing with. Bastard).

Driver 2: The devil is a liar. Premature death is not my portion. I reject it. Do you know who I am? Na because of jazz you dey make mouth. "No weapon fashioned against me shall prosper." My God is bigger than your juju and jazz. Occult power na rubbish power. Try me and I go show you say power pass power. (Is it because of jazz that you are boasting. Occult power is rubbish power. Try me and I will show you that (power pass power) all powers are not equal

Driver 1: *Alaye*, e be like say something dey worry you. "*Were ni e.*" No mention God for this matter. No just try me. Yes, I dey use jazz. My jazz is Jesus. Make I tell you, I dey eat flesh and drink blood (referring to the Holy Communion). If na send dey send you, you don jam fire. Devil incarnate. That's how you go about looking for trouble. Shebi you wan *kpai* for accident, e go soon happen, Amusu! (*Alaye*, it is like something is wrong with you. Do not bring God into this matter and don't mess with me. Yes, I use jazz, my jazz is Jesus. Let me tell you, I eat flesh, and I drink blood. If they sent you (as an agent) you have met your match. Devils incarnate. That is how you go about looking for trouble).

Driver 2: Back to sender, I reject your evil wishes, accident no be my portion. Holy ghost fire. Na you carry your wintch come my side, na so so trouble you go dey get today. Mumu! E no go better for you. I am covered by the blood of Jesus. (Accident is not my portion... It is you that came to jam me with your witchcraft; that's how you meet with trouble after trouble today. Fool, it will not be well with you).

The timely intervention of the police deescalated the tension. However, within seconds, the incident had started trending on the internet as people were recording and posting real time as it is now customary for content creators to use mundane acts to attract viewership and comments on their social media pages.

Data Analysis and Discussion

Power Instances

In the context of the interactions between the two Danfo drivers, power refers to that form of language use to influence or show control over others, whether openly or not. In the text, the utterances show that their verbal power comes from their position as cultural actors. Driver 1 showed traditional understanding of how invocations work. Hence, he implores the god of thunder with the expression, 'God punish you; thunder go fire you and your generation.' Driver 2 also employs the power of personal conviction and denunciation, leaning on the popular Pentecostal quotations 'Back to sender; Holy ghost fire burn you and your entire generation, I reject it, and it's not my portion. Power is also visible as the two drivers' verbal exchanges with with expressions such as, "the use of jazz, My God is bigger than your jazz, I dey eat flesh and drink blood etc. show, that their source of verbal firework is completely drawn from the Pentecostal vernacular forms. Thus, Pentecostal language and discourse often involves powerful metaphors and expressions that can influence power dynamics within social interactions. Analyzing the text shows how individuals can use language to assert their power and dominance, negotiate authority, and establish social hierarchies. These vituperative exchanges reveal the use of warfare language in business and public space outside the precincts of designated worship centers as both powerful weapons of offence and defense.

The incorporation of religious expressions into social interactions within non-sacred spaces highlights the profound impact of Pentecostal theology on the social fabric of the Nigerian people. The populace is aware of the presence of adversaries and their human agents who are perceived to consistently impede social progress. As a result, any perceived act of aggression by a community member capable of impeding another's socioeconomic flourishing as witnessed in the above scenario is considered intolerable. The community regards such perpetrators as enemies of progress. As McAlister points out, the use of scripture in the form of imprecatory prayer has been discreetly employed by individuals, including Christians and non-Christians. References to biblical texts are not

only used strategically to affirm group affiliation and identity but also to cultivate cultural value that can be used to gain respect or to speak authoritatively, extending influence over personal and social spheres of existence (Wariboko, 2016).

Ideological Dimensions

Ideologies are values, opinions and belief systems that shape the way a person or a group thinks, understands the world or acts. Ideologies are related to power because ideological concerns are embedded in some conventions that depend on power relations which underpin and legitimize them. Undeniably, language use is a social behavior through which people enact or project ideologies. Therefore, language is connected to ideology (Fairclough, 2001). The belief system of the people engaged in the war of words underscores their ideological leanings. Hence, the covert ideologies in their language use are those of threat, invocation, imprecation, and reversal.

Ideology of Threat

A threat is a direct or indirect declaration of intent to bring someone harm. Threat is also seen as a situation whereby a person or a group has either the intention or perceived capacity to cause another person some harm (Davis, 2000). Driver 1 resorted to threat after his complaint as an offence strategy. The threat started with the conditional if clause, Driver 1: If you talk nonsense now, I go use this ... You go fix my bus o. You no dey go anywhere... (You will fix my bus. Are you not the one that hit the back of my vehicle? You are not going anywhere. I will teach you a lesson today...). Driver 2: Who you be? Na because of jazz you dey make mouth. "No weapon fashioned against me shall prosper." My God is bigger than your juju and jazz. Occult power na rubbish power. Try me and I go show you say power pass power. Community members, including Christians and non-Christians, share a common belief in the performative power of spoken words to shape or manifest reality, which is rooted in local traditional beliefs. It is for this reason that community members always make sure they cancel curses and negative utterances against them.

Ideology of Invocation and Imprecation

In this ideology, Driver 1 shows belief in the powers of the god of thunder and even God by invoking the supernatural forces on Driver 2. This ideology is visible in the following exchanges: Driver 1: God punish you. Thunder fire you and your generation. E no go better for you. (God will punish you and your generation. It will not be well with you).

Driver 2: "Back to sender," Na you wey him head no correct and na you e no go better for. Holy ghost fire burn you and your entire generation, Mumu. (Back to sender. It's you whose head is not correct and it's you whom it will not be well with. Holy ghost fire burn you and your entire generation. Fool!).

Driver 1: This man, e be like say something dey worry you. "*Were ni e.*" (you are mad). No mention God for this matter. No just try me. Yes, I dey use jazz. My jazz is Jesus. Make I tell you, I dey eat flesh and drink blood (referring to the Holy Communion). If na send dey send you, you don jam fire. Devil incarnate! That's how you go about looking for trouble. Shebi you wan die for accident, e go soon happen, Amusu! (witch). (This man, it's like something is wrong with you. Don't bring God into this matter and don't mess with me. Yes, I use jazz, my jazz is Jesus. Let me tell you, I eat flesh and drink blood. If they sent you (as an agent) you have met your match. Devils incarnate. That is how you go about looking for trouble).

Driver 2: Back to sender, I reject your evil wishes, accident no be my portion. Na you go die first. Holy ghost fire. I am covered by the blood of Jesus. Na you carry your wintch come my side, na so trouble you go dey get today. Mumu! E no go better for you. (Accident is not my portion... It's you that came to jam me with your witchcraft; that's how you meet with trouble after trouble today. Fool, it will not be well with you). Imprecations are curses or abusive use of language to convey an angry, rude, or hostile attitude towards another person. Imprecations are marked by denunciatory or acerbic comments. The worsening economic situation has imbued community members with greater

awareness and suspicion of one another's intentions, leading to labeling to affirm or reject commonly acceptable meanings in ways that recognize the fleeting nature of most daily interpersonal encounters.

Here, the subjects used Pentecostal speak to shape and affirm their social identities. For instance, in this exchange, both parties employed Pentecostal vernacular to express anger and frustrations, aiming to claim victims and pin the other as guilty. When Driver 2 accused driver 1 of boasting confidently because of *juju/jazz* (a spell believed among West Africans, that some people who belong to the occult possess magical or supernatural power to cast a spell or harm somebody), he was drawing on Nigerian and West African cultural belief in the potency of *juju/jazz* and curses, especially, when they are used against an opponent. Language serves as a vehicle for cultural expression and identity formation. The adoption and adaptation of Pentecostal language and rhetoric reflect broader cultural shifts and the influence of religious ideologies on societal norms and practices. The exchange highlights the dynamics of power and defiance, with both parties referencing cultural beliefs and norms. The use of religious language and cultural references further reinforces the subject's identities. Pentecostal influence on language use extends beyond religious contexts to permeate everyday discourse and social exchanges. The proliferation of Pentecostal beliefs and practices has led to the adoption of Pentecostal rhetoric in diverse settings, from politics to popular culture, thereby shaping broader patterns of communication and discourse in Nigerian society.

Ideology of Reversal

In Pentecostal warfare prayers, the 'back to sender,' 'I reject it,' and 'it is not my portion' mantras are ideologies of reversal and denunciation. These expressions are used to return whatever is perceived as coming from the enemy's camp to the victims. It is a defense strategy launched anytime there is a verbal or other form of threat or attack. The ideology of reversal is visible in the following expressions: Driver 1: "*Were ni e.*" ... No just try me. Yes, I dey use jazz. My jazz is Jesus. Make I tell you, I dey eat flesh and drink blood (referring to the Holy Communion). 'If na send dey send you, you don jam fire be dat. The devi is a liar.' That is how you go about looking for trouble. Shebi you wan die for accident, e go soon happen, Amusu!

Driver 2: "Back to sender," Na you wey him head no correct and na you e no go better for' 'Na you God go punish'. 'Make your evil words backfire', 'No weapon fashioned against me shall prosper' (Accident is not my portion... It is you that came to jam me with your witchcraft; that's how you will meet with trouble after trouble today. Fool, it will not be well with you).

The interpretation and significance of a linguistic expression depends heavily on practical experiences and the context in which the linguistic expression is used. Consequently, when confronted with unexpected verbal hostility, the reaction is often spontaneous, involving a defensive response that rebukes the aggressor and dismisses the negative utterances. Common phrases like 'back to sender,' 'blood of Jesus,' 'Holy Ghost fire,' and 'I am covered by the blood of Jesus' are frequently employed, as evidenced in the interactions described in the texts. The prevailing belief is that failing to address such malevolent or negative expressions may result in them becoming a reality.

Identities and Representations

Identities are ideas created in people's minds about themselves as individuals, and how others see them as members of social groups, and they are often reflected in descriptions, nomenclatures, idiosyncrasies that help to identify people. Expressions of identities and how they are represented in the interactions include: *Alaye*, bastard, Devil incarnate, god of thunder, God, the Holy Ghost, Jesus, *ogogoro* drinker, witch, occult, *jazz/juju*, eating flesh and drinking blood.

Driver 1 addresses Driver 2 as *Alaye*, a derogatory way of addressing a male member of the Nigerian society, connoting irresponsibility, or recklessness. Beyond identifying the gender of Driver 2, the driver 1 represents him as someone who drinks *ogogoro* (local dry gin) early in the morning, and as such reinforcing the labelling - irresponsible man who should not be on the road driving. Driver 2 also tried to ridicule and cast aspersion on the person of Driver 2 by accusing him of being an occult man who engages in witchcraft and uses *jazz/juju* for protection as well as to intimidate others. Again,

other forms of identities are seen in the Trinity (god, God, the Holy Ghost and Jesus and The Holy communion metaphorically referred to as drinking blood and eating flesh by driver 1). The Blood of Jesus is represented as a protective weapon (shield) against the onslaughts of an enemy while the Holy Ghost fire is represented as an offensive weapon. God is represented as the giver of justice while the god of thunder is represented as vengeful. Both drivers represent one another as an enemy of progress.

Conclusion

This study explores the widespread integration of Pentecostal expressions into everyday Nigerian discourse, highlighting their role beyond religious settings. Pentecostalism's adept use of mass media and digital platforms has facilitated the diffusion of its theological language, enabling its adaptation and repurposing in popular culture. These expressions, once confined to religious contexts, now function as linguistic coping mechanisms, reflecting individual interpretations rather than fixed religious meanings. The increasing use of Pentecostal expressions correlates with economic instability and social insecurity, which have heightened distrust, frustration, and anxiety. Many Nigerians believe in the performative power of speech, using religious language to navigate challenges and assert control over uncertain realities. This has led to the normalization of terms like "Holy Ghost fire," "it's not my portion," "I reject is," "Blood of Jesus," "anointing," "binding and casting," and many others in everyday interactions. Beyond reinforcing Pentecostal ideologies, these expressions serve as identity markers and are employed even by non-Pentecostals for pragmatic rather than doctrinal purposes. This reflects a broader sociolinguistic trend where spiritual idioms are leveraged to influence discourse and social interactions. By bridging theology, linguistics, sociology, and cultural studies, this study sheds light on how religious language permeates secular spaces. It contributes to an underexplored area of sociolinguistics, offering insights into language evolution, ideological formation, and cultural transformation in Nigeria and beyond.

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